

MINING NON-CONVENTIONAL YEASTS BIODIVERSITY

17TH FEBRUARY 2026

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Meeting organized within the framework of the Non Conventional Yeasts (NCY) diversity project, funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU, Mission M4C2, Investment 1.1, PRIN PNRR 2022 (Project Code P20229JMMH, CUP B53D23024920001).

Organizing Committee

Nicola Vitulo
Giovanna Felis
Benedetta Turchetti
Eugenio Parente
Francesca Di Cesare
Gioele Lazzari
Daniele Andreani

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Scientific Programme

17th February 2026

10:00-10:20: **Nicola Vitulo** – Welcome and introduction to the project

10:20-11:40: Session 1 – Genomics and Bioinformatics:Unlocking Yeast biodiversity – Chair: Nicola Vitulo

10:20-10:40: **Francesca Di Cesare** – Inside *Mrakia*: from genomes to metabolic function

10:40-11:00: **Eugenio Parente** – Metataxonomic insights in the ecology of yeasts in foods

11:00-11:20: **Pranas Grigaitis** – Quantifying the metabolic potential of NCYs using genome-scale metabolic models as tools for knowledge transfer from model yeasts

11:20-11:40: **Francesca Cordero** – How to reveal the function-specific microbial communities: from metagenomic profiling to metabolic models.

11:40-12:00: Coffee break

12:00-13:00: Session 2 – Microbial Collections as Key Infrastructures for Biodiversity and Biotechnology – Chair: Eugenio Parente

12:00-12:20: **Benedetta Turchetti** – Non-conventional yeasts: from the environment to innovative brewing

12:20-12:40: **Neža Čadež** – Adaptation of a thermotolerant *Hanseniaspora* species to European vineyards over the last 20 years

12:40-13:00: **Andrey Yurkov** – Yeast diversity in bee-angiosperm systems in natural and agricultural settings

13:00-14:30: Lunch

14:30-15:50: Session 3 – From Biodiversity to Biotechnology: Harnessing Biological Resources for Innovation – Chair: Giovanna Felis

14:30-14:50: **John Morrissey** – Understanding and exploiting the diversity of sugar transporters in *Kluyveromyces marxianus*

14:50-15:10: **Rosane Schwan** – Non-*Saccharomyces* yeasts in coffee and cocoa fermentation: from microbial ecology to quality attributes

15:10-15:30: **Laura Canonico** – Non-conventional yeasts: exploring biodiversity in brewing

15:30-15:50: **Marilena Budroni** – Type I Sourdough Sardinian Culture Collection: a hub of biodiversity protection

15:50-16:00: **Giovanna Felis** – Concluding remarks

Contributors and affiliations

Nicola Vitulo: Department of Biotechnology, University of Verona, 37134 Verona, Italy

Francesca Di Cesare: Department of Biotechnology, University of Verona, 37134 Verona, Italy; Verona University Culture Collection, Department of Biotechnology, VUCC-DBT, Verona, Italy

Eugenio Parente: Department of Agricultural, Forest, Food and Environmental Sciences, University of Basilicata, 85100 Potenza, Italy

Pranas Grigaitis: Institute for Biological Interfaces (IBG-5), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, 76344 Eggenstein-Leopoldshafen, Germany

Francesca Cordero: Computer Science Department, University of Turin, 10149 Turin, Italy; Laboratorio InfoLife, Consorzio Interuniversitario Nazionale per l'Informatica (CINI), 00185 Rome, Italy

Benedetta Turchetti: Department of Agricultural, Food and Environmental Sciences, University of Perugia, 06121 Perugia, Italy; DBVPG, University of Perugia, 06121 Perugia, Italy

Neža Čadež: University of Ljubljana, Biotechnical Faculty, Department of Food Science, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

Andrey Yurkov: Leibniz Institute DSMZ - German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures, 38124 Braunschweig, Germany

John Morrissey: University College Cork, T12 K8AF, Cork, Ireland

Rosane Schwan: Universidade Federal de Lavras, MG 37203-202 Lavras, Brazil

Laura Canonico: Department of Life and Environmental Sciences, Polytechnic University of Marche, Via Breccie Bianche, 60131 Ancona, Italy.

Marilena Budroni: Department of Agriculture, University of Sassari, 07100 Sassari, Italy; MicroBioDiverSar- University of Sassari Culture Collection, MBDS-UNISSCC, Department of Agriculture, University of Sassari, 07100 Sassari, Italy

Giovanna Felis: Department of Biotechnology, University of Verona, 37134 Verona, Italy; Verona University Culture Collection, Department of Biotechnology, VUCC-DBT, Verona, Italy

Session 1: Genomics and Bioinformatics:Unlocking Yeast biodiversity

Inside *Mrakia*: from genomes to metabolic function

**F. Di Cesare^{1,2}, B. Turchetti^{3,4}, D. Andreani^{3,4}, G. Lazzari¹, E. Parente⁵,
G. Felis^{1,2}, N. Vitulo¹**

¹ Department of Biotechnology, University of Verona, 37134 Verona, Italy

² Verona University Culture Collection, Department of Biotechnology, VUCC-DBT, Verona, Italy

³ Department of Agricultural, Food and Environmental Sciences, University of Perugia, 06121 Perugia, Italy

⁴ DBVPG, University of Perugia, 06121 Perugia, Italy

⁵ Department of Agricultural, Forest, Food and Environmental Sciences, University of Basilicata, 85100 Potenza, Italy

Advances in next-generation sequencing (NGS) and integrated omics have accelerated the exploration of non-conventional yeasts (NCYs), expanding their potential for biotechnological innovation. Within this framework, the psychrophilic and psychrotolerant genus *Mrakia* is a promising but largely uncharacterized group, with evidence of fermentative potential including its recent use in low-alcohol beer experimental production.

During the NCYdiversity project, we generated high-quality genomes and transcriptomes for all 20 *Mrakia* type strains preserved in international Culture Collections. Oxford Nanopore and Illumina sequencing data were jointly used to refine and improve genome assemblies, resulting in highly contiguous and accurate genomes.

Phylogenomic relationships were investigated using average nucleotide identity (ANI) and average amino acid identity (AAI), both of which consistently supported the presence of three distinct clusters within the genus. These clusters were further confirmed by the reconstruction of a species tree based on single-copy orthologous genes, a robust

phylogenomic framework widely applied to minimize the impact of gene duplication and loss and to reliably infer evolutionary relationships.

Gene prediction and functional annotation were guided by transcriptomic data, enabling a confident definition of coding sequences and supporting the investigation of genes potentially involved in fermentation and other metabolic traits of interest.

Beyond genomics, we report preliminary phenotypic results from Biolog substrate utilization assays, providing the first comparative overview of metabolic capabilities across the genus. In parallel, genome-scale metabolic models (GEMs) were generated for selected strains to explore metabolic potential in silico and link genotype to phenotype.

Overall, this work establishes the most comprehensive genomic and phenotypic framework available for *Mrakia* and lays the foundation for its future biotechnological exploitation in sustainable and innovative food processes.

Acknowledgments: This work is conducted within the framework of the Non Conventional Yeasts (NCY) diversity project, funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU, Mission M4C2, Investment 1.1, PRIN PNRR 2022 (Project Code P20229JMMH, CUP B53D23024920001).

Metataxonomic insights in the ecology of yeasts in foods

E. Parente

Department of Agricultural, Forest, Food and Environmental Sciences, University of Basilicata, 85100 Potenza, Italy

In the last 15 years amplicon targeted metagenomics has been increasingly used to characterize the fungal communities of foods and food environments. Even with all its limitations (biases, inability to correctly assigned taxonomies at or below the genus level) high throughput sequencing of marker genes (mostly ITS1 and ITS2 regions, but also 18S and 26S), which are being partly addressed by full-length sequencing of target genes, it has provided a wealth of data on fungal microbial communities. During the NCYdiversity project we have redesigned the FoodMicrobionet to accommodate and integrate these data, providing which is arguably the best level of annotation among existing resources. In this presentation I will illustrate the structure of FoodMicrobionet v5 and navigate through a few case studies which will demonstrate its use in the systematic evaluation of fungal communities (with special emphasis on yeasts) in selected fermented foods (alcoholic beverages, table olives), in the exploration of the distribution of selected taxa in foods, in the inference of microbial association networks and in the exploration of cross-kingdom networks in foods in which both bacteria and fungi drive the fermentation.

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Quantifying the metabolic potential of NCYs using genome-scale metabolic models as tools for knowledge transfer from model yeasts

P. Grigaitis

Institute for Biological Interfaces (IBG-5), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, 76344 Eggenstein-Leopoldshafen, Germany

Genome-scale metabolic models (GEMs) are computational tools that represent the complete metabolism of an organism by including all known biochemical reactions and their stoichiometry. They are valuable for exploring the metabolic capabilities of organisms, particularly in metabolic engineering. Initially, GEMs were developed for model organisms, but advances in genome sequencing and increased interest in metabolic engineering have led to the creation of new GEMs for a broader array of organisms. In my talk, I will briefly reflect on the evolution of yeast metabolic modeling in the last 20 years from the very first GEM of budding yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* published in 2003. I will discuss how the vast amount of knowledge, encoded in the GEM of *S. cerevisiae*, can be transferred to other yeasts, including the NCYs. As a case study, we will consider the recently-published GEM for an industrially-relevant NCY *Pichia kluyveri*, used for the production of alcohol-free beverages, such as alcohol-free beer. I will show how *P. kluyveri* vs. *S. cerevisiae* GEMs enabled a comprehensive analysis of microbial physiology- and -omics data, and helped us to reason the metabolic phenotypes and behaviors the NCY *P. kluyveri* employs. I will make a point for the potential role of reconstructing GEMs in large-scale studies searching for “new biochemistry” in NCYs and beyond.

How to reveal the function-specific microbial communities: from metagenomic profiling to metabolic models.

M. Beccuti^{1,2}, S. Pernice^{1,2}, R. Aucello¹, L. Chiabrando¹, S. Gepiro Contaldo^{1,2}, D. Tortarolo¹, F. Cordero^{1,2}

¹ Computer Science Department, University of Turin, 10149 Turin, Italy

² Laboratorio InfoLife, Consorzio Interuniversitario Nazionale per l'Informatica (CINI), 00185 Rome, Italy

Taxonomic profiling and functional analysis have become routine for characterising microbial community compositions and functions across diverse microbiological systems. However, these descriptive approaches do not determine which assembly of microorganisms is optimal to perform a specified metabolic function [1].

A computational framework that integrates taxonomic assignments with genome-scale metabolic models (GEMs) via computational modeling enables rational design of function-specific microbial consortia. The pipeline begins with shotgun metagenomic sequencing of microbial communities, followed by annotation via taxonomic sequence classifiers and abundance estimation to generate standardised microbial profiles. These taxonomic labels are then systematically mapped to organism-specific GEMs via databases of metabolic reconstructions, bridging the gap between observational sequencing data and metabolic modelling.

Once taxonomic labels are assigned to metabolic reconstructions, the framework formulates community assembly as a combinatorial optimisation problem. Taxa presence is treated as a binary decision variable, and the objective is to denoise community complexity while satisfying target metabolic flux requirements. The resulting problems can be solved efficiently using Linear Programming (LP) solvers, yielding minimal consortia that achieve user-defined functional outcomes, including metabolite production, nutrient depletion, or the establishment of a cross-feeding network.

The analytical framework bridges automated metagenomic workflows with optimisation-driven community design. Sequencing post-processing platforms and classification pipelines generate taxonomic profiles, which users submit to a web-based automated service for the subsequent stages of community metabolic reconstruction and functional optimisation.

The generality of the approach extends across microbial systems diversity (*e.g.*, human gut microbiomes, environmental systems, and industrial reactors). Such a framework is suitable for the computational exploration of alternative non-conventional yeast communities capable of achieving desired fermentation phenotypes (ethanol yield, flavour compound synthesis, and response to growth conditions) [2]. By reframing taxonomic biodiversity data as input to metabolic engineering problems, the method transforms microbial resource collections from reference databases into operational design spaces for biotechnological implementations.

References:

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- [2] Zhang, J., Wang, S. & Nielsen, J. Recent advances in systems and synthetic biology approaches for developing novel cell-factories in non-conventional yeasts. *Biotechnol. Adv.* 47, 107695 (2021)

Session 2: Microbial Collections as Key Infrastructures for Biodiversity and Biotechnology

Non-conventional yeasts: from the environment to innovative brewing

B. Turchetti^{1,2}, C. Sannino^{1,2}, G. Mugnai³, P. Buzzini^{1,2}

¹ Department of Agricultural, Food and Environmental Sciences, University of Perugia, 06121 Perugia, Italy

² DBVPG, University of Perugia, 06121 Perugia, Italy

³ Department of Agronomy Food Natural Resources Animals and Environment, University of Padova, 35020, Legnaro, Padova, Italy

Fermentative yeasts have been deliberately — and at times unintentionally — used in the food industry for centuries, with brewing representing one of the earliest and most widespread applications. In recent years, the employment of non-conventional brewing yeasts as alternative starter cultures has emerged as a highly promising strategy. To date, most documented brewing processes involving non-conventional yeasts have focused on ascomycetous species, whereas much less is known about the potential of basidiomycetous taxa.

A growing number of ecological studies conducted in cold environments around the world have revealed a notable presence of basidiomycetous yeasts in these habitats. In the framework of a dual approach (metagenomic and culturomic), over a thousand of psychrophilic yeast strains have been isolated and preserved in the DBVPG Industrial Yeasts Collection (Perugia, Italy). These organisms exhibit unique physiological and metabolic adaptations that allow them to withstand extremely low temperatures. Among these, the fermentative capability of the genus *Mrakia* sets it apart from most other cold-adapted yeasts.

Because of their low optimal growth temperatures and the limited ethanol they produce during fermentation, certain *Mrakia* species appear particularly suitable as starter cultures for low-alcohol beer production. Consequently, species within the genus *Mrakia* were examined to evaluate

their fermentative potential and to better understand how these traits relate to their taxonomy and ecological functions.

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Adaptation of a thermotolerant *Hanseniaspora* species to European vineyards over the last 20 years

N. Čadež, K. Doberšek

University of Ljubljana, Biotechnical Faculty, Department of Food Science, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

Yeasts of the *Hanseniaspora* genus are considered to be the most widespread yeast genus on grapes and in fresh grape juice, where they have a significant influence on sensory properties of wines. Although *Hanseniaspora* yeasts and the wine yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* often occupy the same ecological niche, their evolutionary pathways are fundamentally different. *Hanseniaspora* yeasts are characterized by accelerated evolution - the two main mechanisms driving the evolution of *Hanseniaspora* are genome downsizing through gene loss (removal of non-essential genes in certain environments) and genetic variability driven primarily by hypermutation.

H. opuntiae species was initially isolated from natural environment in Hawaii, and only after the year 2000 it began to emerge in isolates from European vineyards, slowly displacing the native *H. uvarum*. Therefore, we hypothesize that *H. opuntiae* may be a non-native species to European vineyards spreading easily due to its thermotolerance and other specific phenotypic advantages over *H. uvarum* in novel environments. Using high-throughput phenotyping Pyphe [1], we characterized of a collection of *H. uvarum* and *H. opuntiae* isolates from different ecological niches under selective conditions that reflect the anthropogenic influences on the vineyard and winemaking environment and the effects of climate change that critically affect the population structure of these species. As selective growth conditions, we tested the fungicides commonly used in Slovenia and some other growth inhibitors commonly used in wine-making. *H. opuntiae* showed a higher tolerance to most of the stress factors tested, supporting the hypothesis of its competitive advantage in vineyards.

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Pyphe, a python toolbox for assessing microbial growth and cell viability in high-throughput colony screens, *eLife* **9**:e55160 (2020)

Yeast diversity in bee-angiosperm systems in natural and agricultural settings

A. Yurkov¹, S. Erler^{2,3}, H. Greil², H. Gardein², K. Wueppenhorst², Y. Kovalova¹, M. Neumann-Schaal¹, B. Turchetti^{4,5}

¹ Leibniz Institute DSMZ - German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures, 38124 Braunschweig, Germany

² Institute for Bee Protection, Julius Kuehn-Institute, 38124 Braunschweig, Germany

³ Zoological Institute, Technische Universität Braunschweig, 38124 Braunschweig, Germany

⁴ Department of Agricultural, Food and Environmental Sciences, University of Perugia, 06121 Perugia, Italy

⁵ DBVPG, University of Perugia, Borgo XX Giugno 74, Perugia, Italy

Plant-pollinator mutualisms have profoundly shaped the diversity of terrestrial ecosystems. Bees are the most important pollinators of crops and wild plants, and the diversity of wild bees, their ecological niches, and nutritional strategies span a wide range of plants. Among the organisms that closely interact with both plants and pollinators, microscopic prokaryotes and eukaryotes play a key but still insufficiently explored role. Particularly, yeasts inhabit plant-associated niches and are tightly linked to pollinators through shared resources such as nectar and pollen, as well as through habitats including plant surfaces and underground nests. Despite the fact that insects represent biodiversity hotspots for yeasts, the diversity of bee-associated yeasts and their functions remain poorly understood.

In a series of studies conducted in Germany, we investigated the diversity of nectar-inhabiting and bee-associated yeasts and their interactions with honey bees and wild bees. We examined how yeast communities respond to habitat heterogeneity, particularly plant diversity, and to environmental stressors such as agrochemicals. A second research focus addressed the diversity and potential benefits of yeasts associated with oligolectic bees throughout their developmental cycle. In parallel, we studied the effects of yeasts on pollinators mediated through chemical modification of nectar.

Our results show that yeast diversity changes progressively during the early vegetative season, with early-emerging wild bees contributing to the initial inoculation of nectar yeasts. Overwintering yeasts in bee nests

are actively transferred to subsequent generations via provisions and eggs. As fungi, yeasts respond to fungicides, although resilience and recovery differ between taxa. Typical nectar yeasts exhibit high tolerance to agrochemicals and extreme sugar concentrations, utilize plant-derived amino acids, and transform sugars into alcohols, acids, and ethers. These metabolites are not cross-assimilated by co-occurring species, suggesting chemical niche partitioning within nectar.

Future research should focus on preservation of bee provisions, nutrient consolidation and detoxification processes.

Session 3: From Biodiversity to Biotechnology: Harnessing Biological Resources for Innovation

Understanding and exploiting the diversity of sugar transporters in *Kluyveromyces marxianus*

J. Morrissey

University College Cork, T12 K8AF, Cork, Ireland

The yeast *Kluyveromyces marxianus* has been isolated from diverse environments but its main habitat appears to be decaying plant material. Secreted enzymes enable the yeast access plant polysaccharides such as pectin and fructans and *K. marxianus* is able to assimilate a wide array of sugars, including monosaccharides and disaccharides. This capacity to use a wide range of sugars is due to an extensive repertoire of sugar transporters, many of which have arisen from gene duplication and diversification events. As well as wild habitats, *K. marxianus* is frequently isolated from specific anthropogenic environments, notably agave and dairy fermentations. In both cases, there is evidence of niche specialisation, and in the dairy environment, it is now clear that the species has become domesticated. The dairy domestication appears to have been driven by intraspecies hybridisation and subsequent adaptation. The strongest phenotype of this domestication is improved lactose fermentation. This is due to specific polymorphisms in the gene encoding the Lac12 transporter that increase the capacity to transport lactose. This trait can be exploited in biotechnology as it also enables *K. marxianus* grown on lactose-containing side streams such as whey permeate. This presentation will discuss the diversity, evolution and specialisation of sugar transporters in *K. marxianus* as well as work to develop this yeast for biotechnology.

Non-*Saccharomyces* yeasts in coffee and cocoa fermentation: from microbial ecology to quality attributes

R. Schwan

Universidade Federal de Lavras, MG 37203-202 Lavras, Brazil

Coffee and cocoa fermentations represent biologically complex bioprocesses in which microbial biodiversity can be strategically harnessed to enhance product quality and process efficiency. Beyond the conventional use of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, non-*Saccharomyces* yeasts have emerged as valuable biotechnological resources due to their metabolic versatility, enzymatic potential, and contribution to flavour diversification. This presentation explores the biotechnological relevance of non-*Saccharomyces* yeasts in coffee and cocoa fermentations, integrating microbial ecology with quality-driven innovation. In cocoa fermentation, yeasts dominate the initial stages and are responsible for pulp degradation, ethanol production, and the generation of key volatile and non-volatile metabolites that trigger downstream microbial succession and internal bean transformations. Species such as *Pichia kluyveri*, *Pichia kudriavzevii*, *Hanseniaspora uvarum*, *Torulaspota delbrueckii*, and *Kluyveromyces marxianus* exhibit high fermentative robustness and enzymatic activities, including pectinolytic and glycosidic functions, leading to improved flavour precursor formation and enhanced chocolate sensory profiles when applied as starter cultures. Similarly, coffee fermentation systems, across dry, semi-dry, and wet processing, in aerobic, semi-anaerobic, or anaerobic processes, benefit from the application of non-*Saccharomyces* yeasts with targeted metabolic

traits. Selected strains of *Torulaspora delbrueckii*, *Pichia fermentans*, *P. kluyveri*, and *H. uvarum* have demonstrated the ability to modulate organic acid balance, increase ester and higher alcohol production, and improve beverage aroma complexity and sensory scores. Comparative analysis reveals that, despite distinct substrates and processing conditions, yeast-driven metabolic pathways are central to flavour development in both coffee and cocoa fermentations. From a biotechnological perspective, the selection and application of non-*Saccharomyces* starter cultures offer a powerful strategy to control fermentation, enhance reproducibility, and tailor sensory outcomes while preserving product identity. Harnessing native yeast biodiversity as functional starter cultures aligns fermentation practices with sustainable innovation and adds value to specialty coffee and fine cocoa production.

Non-conventional yeasts: exploring biodiversity in brewing

L. Canonico, F. Comitini, M. Ciani

Department of Life and Environmental Sciences, Polytechnic University of Marche,
Via Breccie Bianche, 60131 Ancona, Italy.

The brewing industry has historically relied almost exclusively on the use of strains belonging to the species *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (Ale Beer) and *Saccharomyces pastorianus* (Lager beer) resulting in a predictable and often limited range of beer flavors. However, in recent years, many studies were focused on the crucial role of yeast biodiversity in modern brewing innovation, especially towards the world of non-conventional yeasts (NCYs). The use of NCYs allows brewers to diversify beer flavors, developing no-alcohol and low-alcohol (NABLAB), and functional or fortified beers. The key to their success lies not just in their fermentation efficiency, which can sometimes be limited, but to their capacity to produce a wide range of volatile and nonvolatile compounds, like esters, higher alcohols, and acids, that profoundly enhance the finished product's flavor and aroma. These yeasts represent a huge source of biodiversity, offering brewers the ability to move beyond the traditional Ale and Lager classifications to develop true specialty beers. These innovative products, which include low-calorie and gluten-free options, are perfectly suited for the unique contributions of non-conventional strains. The success of these new strains must always be carefully evaluated alongside other factors, particularly the substrate and the specific beer style you intend to produce. Exploring this microbial diversity is not only a scientific goal but represents a significant step toward a biologically rich future for the world of beer.

Type I Sourdough Sardinian Culture Collection: a hub of Biodiversity Protection

M. Budroni^{1,2}, R. Coronas^{1,2}, A. Bianco¹, L. Sanna^{1,2}, G. Zara^{1,2}

¹ Department of Agriculture, University of Sassari, 07100 Sassari, Italy

² MicroBioDiverSar- University of Sassari Culture Collection, MBDS-UNISSCC, Department of Agriculture, University of Sassari, 07100 Sassari, Italy

Traditional type I sourdoughs are being rediscovered and increasingly used in artisanal and industrial bakeries due to the unique taste and texture, potential health benefits, and longer shelf life they confer on baked products. These unique properties are attributed to the diverse microbial communities of sourdough, comprising both yeasts and bacteria. The traditional preservation method for type I sourdough (i.e., continuous backslopping) may lead, over time, to taxonomic and functional rearrangements of its microbial communities. Consequently, significant deviations in the characteristics of baked products can occur. In this context, preservation and maintenance strategies for type I sourdough will be explored, highlighting the essential role that microbial biological resource centres (mBRCs) could play in preserving, sharing, and supporting sourdough microbiomes and citizen science strategies. Moreover, it will address the impact of type I sourdough on the digestibility and nutritional quality of the resulting breads, using Sardinian sourdoughs and *Triticum durum* semolina cv. Senatore Cappelli as a case study.

